

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH ENSURING INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the possibilities of consistent formation of students' intellectual development within the framework of three main periods - reproductive, intellectual-productive and predictive stages. At the initial stage, the role of didactic games, problem situations, and interactive exercises that arouse interest in learning and internal motivation will be highlighted. At the next, substantive-process stage, a system of tasks that serve to develop the skills of analysis, logical conclusion, argumentation and critical thinking is considered. At the final, predictive stage, pedagogical tools aimed at the student's independent scientific and creative research, creation of new knowledge and conscious management of his intellectual activity are analyzed.

Keywords: intellectual, interest, education, student, knowledge, analysis, pedagogical system, memory, attention, thinking, methodical solutions, educational tasks, development, processes

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In the modern educational process, the correct design of educational tasks is the main condition not only for mastering knowledge, but also for the full realization of the emotional and intellectual potential of students. Success in education depends, first of all, on the effectiveness of the assignments, on the ability to encourage the student to think, to invite him to research, and to be structured taking into account individual capabilities. From this point of view, the intellectual development of students is considered as a complex pedagogical system that is carried out continuously and step by step; its effectiveness directly depends on the teacher's methodical approaches, tools and organizational decisions that are oriented towards the individual.

In the educational process, there are opportunities for intellectual development of students divided into three main periods. They are reproductive, intellectual-productive and predictive stages. The process of intellectual development of students is a complex pedagogical system that is implemented continuously and step by step. The effectiveness of this process directly depends on the pedagogical tools used by the teacher, methodical approaches, and the level of consideration of the individual characteristics of students. At the initial stage, the system of pedagogical tools is focused on actively involving students in educational activities, encouraging them to know, observe, search, ask questions, and express their opinions. The main goal of the teacher in this period is to form a positive attitude and internal motivation in students towards learning. At this stage, the teacher uses various didactic games, problem situations, interactive exercises, creative tasks and educational experiments to engage students in intellectual activity. In this way, students gradually begin to understand their place as subjects of the cognitive process, their thinking, memory, attention and perception abilities begin to develop actively. At the second stage, the teacher's attention is focused on the meaningful-process direction of intellectual development of students. During this period, students develop not only an interest in learning, but also intellectual and practical skills such as analyzing the learned information, connecting them with real life examples, making logical conclusions, and justifying their opinion with evidence. At this stage, the teacher activates their thinking process by offering problematic questions, analytical tasks, and small scientific researches to the students. As a result, students learn to independently form their own opinion, to justify it logically and to take a critical approach. It is during this period that students' individual characteristics, natural talents, tendency to analytical thinking and creative potential begin to manifest themselves. The task of the teacher is to identify these

characteristics, guide them, encourage and develop them. At the third stage, the system of pedagogical tools is directed to the formation of intellectual, emotional and voluntary activity skills in students. During this period, the student is not only a receiver of ready-made knowledge, but becomes an active person who analyzes them and strives to independently create new knowledge. He can justify his opinion logically, approaches problems creatively, shows independence in decision-making. At the same time, at this stage emotional-intellectual balance is formed, i.e. students can confidently defend their opinion, accept critical opinions correctly, and be able to control themselves. As a result, the three stages of intellectual development as a single system strengthen students' need for knowledge, ensure their thinking culture, self-awareness and personal growth.

REFERENCES USED

1. Маслоу А. Мотивация и личность. Питер: СПб., 2003. 352 с.
2. Рубинштейн С.Л. Основы общей психологии.– СПб.: Питер, 2006.-с. 713.
3. Леонтов А.В. Модель научной школы и практика организации исследовательской деятельности учащихся // Школьные технологии. – М., 2001. –№5. – С 147-148
3. Davletshin M.G. Zamonaviy maktab o'qituvchisining psixologiyasi. –Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 1999. –30 b.
4. Safarova R.G va b. O'quvchilarda o'zaro do'stona munosabatlarga asoslanib hamkorlikda faoliyat ko'rsatish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish jarayonini tashkil etish tamoyillari va parametrlari//Monografiya. Toshkent: "Fan va texnologiya", 2013.
5. Adizov B.R. Boshlang'ich ta'limni ijodiy tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari. Pedagogika fanlari doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiyasi. - T.: 2002.-276 b.
6. Суртаева Н.Н. //Интеллектуальные процессы в образовании взрослых как фактор развития интеллектуального и социокультурного потенциала регионов. Монография. - СПб.: Тюмень: ТОГИРРО, 2001.
7. Каменский А.М. Методическая поддержка индивидуального развития школьников на занятиях по физике: Дисс. ...канд. пед. наук.–СПб.,1999.–21 с.
8. Назмутдинова М.А. Управление учебной деятельностью учащихся в условиях индивидуализации и дифференциации обучения//: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. – Казань, 1994
9. Есев А.Н. Соотношение индивидуальных и надиндивидуальных факторов ценностных ориентаций личности как методологическая проблема: Дисс. ... канд. филос. наук. – Ставрополь, 1999. – 153 с.
10. Safarova R.G., Nurjanova R.U va b. Fanlarni chuqurlashtirilib o'qitiladigan sinflarda ta'limni tashkil etish texnologiyasi // Toshkent: "Sano-standart" 2012. –5.
11. Saliyeva S.A Individual ta'limning zamonaviy mutaxassis tayyorlashdagi ahamiyati.//Nam.D.U ilmiy axborotnomasi, [2025-9]